

CARRIER LIABILITY INSURANCE FOR INTERNATIONAL ROAD TRANSPORT OF GOODS: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract: Freight transportation by road plays a crucial role in the modern economy, ensuring the delivery of goods and materials to various destinations. However, this process is fraught with risks such as damage or loss of cargo, which can lead to significant financial losses for transportation participants. In this context, carrier liability insurance becomes a relevant risk management tool and protection for the interests of the parties involved. This paper examines the specifics of carrier liability insurance in road freight transportation, analyzes its advantages and disadvantages, and offers recommendations for optimizing this process.

Keywords: Carrier liability insurance, road freight transportation, risk management, financial protection, cargo insurance, insurance coverage, transportation risks

Аннотация: Перевозка грузов автомобильным транспортом играет важную роль в современной экономике, обеспечивая доставку товаров и материалов в различные точки назначения. Однако данный процесс сопряжен с рисками, такими как повреждение или утрата груза, что может привести к значительным финансовым потерям для участников перевозки. В этой связи страхование ответственности перевозчика становится актуальным инструментом управления рисками и защиты интересов сторон. В данной работе будут рассмотрены особенности страхования ответственности перевозчика при перевозке грузов автомобильным транспортом, проанализированы его преимущества и недостатки, а также предложены рекомендации по оптимизации данного процесса.

Ключевые слова: Страхование ответственности перевозчика, перевозка грузов автомобильным транспортом, управление рисками, финансовая защита, страхование грузов, страховое покрытие, риски перевозки

Annotatsiya: Avtotransportda yuk tashish zamonaviy iqtisodiyotda muhim rol o'ynaydi, bu tovarlar va materiallarni turli manzillarga etkazib berishni ta'minlaydi. Ammo bu jarayon yukning shikastlanishi yoki yo'qolishi kabi xavflar bilan bog'liq bo'lib, bu tashish ishtirokchilari uchun katta moliyaviy yo'qotishlarga olib kelishi mumkin. Shu munosabat bilan tashuvchining

javobgarligini sug'urtalash xavflarni boshqarish vositasi va tomonlarning manfaatlarini himoya qilish uchun dolzarb vositaga aylanadi. Ushbu maqolada avtotransportda yuk tashishda tashuvchining javobgarligini sug'urtalash xususiyatlari, uning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari tahlil qilinadi hamda ushbu jarayonni optimallashtirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tashuvchining javobgarligini sug'urtalash, avtotransportda yuk tashish, xavflarni boshqarish, moliyaviy himoya, yuk sug'urtasi, sug'urta qamrovi, tashish xavflari.

Introduction

International road transport of goods plays a crucial role in the modern economy, ensuring the delivery of goods and materials to various destinations. However, this process is associated with risks such as damage or loss of cargo, which can lead to significant financial losses for the parties involved in the transportation. In this context, carrier liability insurance becomes a relevant tool for risk management and protection of the interests of the parties. The legislation in Uzbekistan, specifically the Law on Mandatory Insurance of Carrier Liability, establishes comprehensive regulations to ensure the effective implementation of this insurance system. [1]

This article aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the legal aspects of carrier liability in international road transport of goods, examine insurance mechanisms, their advantages, and disadvantages. The article will also offer recommendations for improving the regulatory framework and introducing innovative technologies to enhance the effectiveness of carrier liability insurance. Implementing these measures will contribute to better risk management and increased trust between the participants in the transportation process. A critical analysis of the regulatory framework and practical aspects of carrier liability insurance when transporting goods by road in Uzbekistan is carried out.

Methods

The research methodology includes a critical analysis of scientific literature, regulatory acts, and industry publications related to the insurance of carrier liability in road freight transportation. Additionally, existing practices and approaches to insurance in this field were studied, and statistical data on cases of damage during transportation were analyzed. The main source of data for this study is the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Uzbekistan on the measures to implement the Law on Mandatory Insurance of Carrier Liability.

Results

Carrier liability insurance in road freight transportation is mandatory according to the legislation of Uzbekistan. The insurance policy covers risks associated with damage, loss, or delay in cargo delivery, as well as harm caused to third parties during transportation. [2] The key provisions of the legislation include the determination of the insurance amount, the procedures for concluding and terminating insurance contracts, and the rights and obligations of the parties involved.

Key provisions

1. **Insurance Amount:** The insurance amount per passenger is set at 44 million UZS, with 40 million UZS allocated for compensation for harm to life or health and 4 million UZS for damage to property.

2. **Contractual Obligations:** Carriers are required to insure their liability before commencing transportation services. The insurance contract is public and valid for one year, except for specific cases where shorter durations are permitted.

3. **Claim Settlement:** The insurer must issue the insurance policy within three working days after receiving the insurance premium. In the event of a claim, the insurer has 15 days to notify the carrier of the decision to pay or deny the claim. [3]

The main advantages of carrier liability insurance include:

1. Protection of the financial interests of transportation participants (shipper, consignee, and carrier) in the event of insured events. [4]

2. Increased trust between transportation parties and the formation of a positive image of the carrier. [5]

3. The ability for the carrier to compensate for losses related to harm caused to third parties during transportation.

However, there are certain disadvantages of this type of insurance:

1. High cost of insurance premiums, especially for carriers transporting hazardous or high-value cargo. [6]

2. Complexity of the claims settlement process, involving the need to prove the occurrence of an insured event and determine the amount of damage. [7]

3. Limitations in insurance coverage concerning certain types of cargo or transportation routes.

Discussion

Based on the conducted analysis, it can be concluded that carrier liability insurance in road freight transportation is an important risk management tool but requires improvement to enhance its efficiency and accessibility. Mandatory

carrier liability insurance provides significant benefits, including the protection of the financial interests of transportation participants, increased trust between parties, and the ability for carriers to compensate for damages caused to third parties. However, several issues need to be addressed to improve the effectiveness and accessibility of this insurance system.

To address the identified issues, the following recommendations are proposed: 1. Develop and implement flexible insurance programs that consider the specifics of the transported cargo and routes, as well as the carrier's loss history; 2. Simplify the claims settlement procedure through the introduction of digital technologies and process automation; 3. Create incentive systems for carriers demonstrating high safety levels and low loss rates; 4. Increase awareness among transportation participants about the specifics of liability insurance and its advantages.

Based on this analysis, the following advantages and disadvantages can be highlighted:

Advantages: 1. Financial protection of the interests of shippers, consignees, and carriers in the event of insured events; 2. Trust and reputation: It enhances trust between transportation participants and helps build a positive image of the carrier; 3. Compensation mechanism: It provides a mechanism for carriers to compensate for damages caused to third parties during transportation.

Disadvantages: 1. The cost of insurance premiums is high for carriers transporting hazardous or high-value cargo; 2. It requires proof of the occurrence of an insured event and determination of the amount of damage; [8] 3. There are restrictions in insurance coverage for certain types of cargo or transportation routes.

Recommendations

To address the identified issues, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. It is necessary to develop and implement flexible insurance programs that consider the specifics of the transported cargo and routes, as well as the carrier's loss history. [9]

2. Simplify the claims settlement process through the introduction of digital technologies and process automation. [10]

3. Create an incentive system for carriers demonstrating high safety levels and low loss rates. [11]

4. Increase awareness among transportation participants about the specifics of liability insurance and its advantages. [12]

Conclusion

Carrier liability insurance in road freight transportation is an important element of the risk management system in this field. Despite existing disadvantages, this type of insurance provides financial protection for transportation participants and helps increase their trust in each other. To improve the efficiency of carrier liability insurance, it is necessary to enhance the legislative framework, introduce innovative technologies, and develop cooperation between insurance companies and transportation participants. Further research should focus on the implementation of these recommendations and continuous monitoring of the insurance system's effectiveness.

This study highlights the importance of carrier liability insurance in road freight transportation and provides a comprehensive analysis of the regulatory framework and practical aspects in Uzbekistan. The proposed recommendations aim to improve the accessibility and efficiency of this essential risk management tool.

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